

Review Article

Independent 3'untranslated region RNA, a novel non-coding regulator RNA: what do we know now?

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Abstract

An independent 3'untranslated region RNA (I3'UTR) is a non-coding RNA, which consists only of the 3'untranslated region of an mRNA, and exists in cells independently, detached from its original mRNA. As presently known, I3'UTRs are expressed from the promoters in the 3'untranslated region of protein-coding genes. In the past twenty years, studies on this type of RNA were only sporadically published, but it was noticed that tumor suppression was a common function of all the I3'UTRs in these studies. Recently, evidence has been presented that the I3'UTRs generally exist in eukaryotes, and are a novel regulating RNA species that is worth of thorough and in-depth investigations. In this mini-review, so-far known properties of I3'UTR are described and potential directions of further studies on this topic are proposed.

Keywords

independent 3'UTR RNA, novel non-coding regulator RNA, tumor suppression

Introduction

Classically, the 3'untranslated region (3'UTR) is that region in eukaryotic protein-coding genes from the translation termination codon to the polyA signal (AATAAA). It is transcribed as an integral part of the mRNA encoded by the gene. The 3'UTR is an important regulation element for the mRNA: it is the site of interaction of the mRNA with various cellular regulatory factors. The mRNA 3'UTR controls translation efficiency of the mRNA [1] through regulation of its stability [2], determines localization [3] of protein product through a localization signal within 3'UTR [4-11], controls recognition of special codons, *e.g.* UGA as selenocystine [12,13], and regulates cellular normal growth, differentiation and proliferation: structural changes within the 3'UTR often cause anomalies in cellular metabolism, and even diseases, such as rheumatoid arthritis, congenital heart disease and type 2 diabetes [14-19]. The mRNA 3'UTR is controlled by microRNAs through interactions of the latter with complementary sequences in the mRNA[20]. Although the functions of classical 3'UTR are so manifold, these functions can be exerted only through the regulation of its own mRNA, and more exactly, through the protein products translated from the mRNA where the 3'UTR is located.

However, there exists another kind of RNA, which consists of the 3'UTR alone, without all other elements in mRNA such as 5'UTR and coding region. Although its sequence is the same as the classical 3'UTR in corresponding mRNA, it plays a different role to that of full-length mRNA. Such kind of 3'UTR RNA can be called "independent 3'UTR RNA" or "3'UTR-associated RNA (uaRNA)"[21].

The importance of independent 3'UTR RNA (hereafter referred as I3'UTR) was prompted by results of artificially introducing such RNA species into malignant mammalian cells. Results indicated that they have important regulatory functions for cell life (see below). And later, bioinformatic and hybridization studies [21-22] confirmed that the I3'UTR does actually exist in human, mouse and fruit fly cells. Nevertheless, until now, only sporadic reports relevant to I3'UTR were published, and the molecular biology of I3'UTR remains unknown.

In this mini-review, based on the reports available presently, the revealed properties of several I3'UTRs are described in detail and their possible functions in cellular and individual development are discussed, aiming at attracting the attention of the biological sciences community and proposing potential directions of further studies on this topic.

Transfection studies on I3'UTRs

Since 1991, several investigations on artificial I3'UTRs' tumor suppression activity were published. There were seven I3'UTRs reported in total [22-35].

To screen for cDNAs with the potential of tumor suppression, a pcD2 expression plasmid library of normal human cDNA was used to transfect DT cells, a malignant mouse cell line containing active RAS genes. From the stable, flat, revertant transfectants, a cDNA clone was obtained which, on re-transfection into DT, gave rise to similar flat revertants, indicating that it had tumor suppression activity [23]. This clone contained a cDNA insert of 0.28 kb long, and sequencing revealed that it was the middle part of the 3'UTR of the human nuclear factor for interleukin-6 (NF-IL6) or C/EBP β gene [24,25].

Subsequent studies showed that transfection of C/EBP β 3'UTR led to down-regulation of several genes

favorable for malignancy and to up-regulation of some genes favorable for phenotypic reversion[26]. Also, it was shown that the sequences near the termini of the C/EBP β 3'UTR were important for its tumor suppression activity[27]. Then, the C/EBP β 3'UTR was found to directly inhibit the phosphorylation activity of protein kinase C ϵ (PKC ϵ) in SMMC-7721, a hepatocarcinoma cell line[28]. Recently, an AU-rich region in the C/EBP β 3'UTR was found also to be responsible for its tumor suppression [29].

Similarly, a normal rat cDNA library, cloned also in pcD2 plasmid, was used to transfect 18T3Y1 cells, a rat cell line malignantly transformed by HPV18 E6 and E7 genes. The transfection of the rat cDNA library also produced revertant cell strains with suppressed tumorigenicity, and a cDNA clone was isolated from the revertant transfectants: it harbored a 0.2kb rat cDNA insert that was found to be the 3'UTR of the mel-18 gene, encoding a highly conserved DNA binding protein [30].

In another paper, a cloned and expressible 0.2kb fragment of the α -tropomyosin gene 3'UTR was transfected into NMU2, a malignant mutant myogenic cell line giving rise to rhabdomyosarcomas in mice. Constitutive expression of RNA from the 0.2 kb fragment of the α -tropomyosin (Tm) 3'UTR, but not control 3'UTRs, was found to suppress anchorage-independent growth and tumor formation by NMU2 cells. And when the 3'UTR RNA expression was extinguished, tumors were formed. These results showed that suppression of tumorigenicity was dependent on the continued expression of Tm 3'UTR[31].

The tumor suppression by RNA from 3'UTR of the α -tropomyosin gene prompted and promoted a study on the possible tumor suppression by the 3'UTR of the ribonuclease reductase subunits R1 and R2. The expression plasmids harboring the 3'UTRs from R1 (446 bp) and R2 (876 bp) genes were transfected into malignant RMP-6 and HeLa cells. The R1 and R2 transfectants of both cell lines were found to have suppressed tumorigenicity[32].

In a study on the anti-proliferative activity of prohibitin, it was found that this activity resides in the 3'UTR. Therefore, the researchers examined the tumor suppression activity of the 3'UTR: They cloned the prohibitin 3'UTR into a eukaryotic expression plasmid, and transfected the breast cancer cell line MCF7 with that recombinant plasmid. The stable transfectants all showed reduced ability of growing in soft agar and reduced tumorigenicity in nude mice. Therefore, the 3'UTR of prohibitin exerted significant tumor suppression activity. And when this 3'UTR underwent mutation, its tumor suppression activity decreased [33-34].

On the other hand, the 3'UTR fragment from HP8, a new member of the C/EBP gene family (it is actually the transcript variant 1 of the C/EBP α), was found to have activity of suppressing the growth of SMMC-7721 hepatocarcinoma cells [35].

All the above mentioned studies on the seven 3'UTRs used DNA fragments within the 3'UTR of

different genes to transfect into different malignant cells, but all of them resulted in significant tumor suppression. This indicated that the 3'UTRs that are separated from their original mRNAs are functional in living cells, and the tumor suppression activity is the most significant function, common for all the 3'UTR RNA species, no matter what the functions of the proteins encoded by the original mRNAs are.

Evidence for existence of I3'UTRs in human, rat, mouse and fly

In the study by Mercer *et al.* [21], it was indicated that a significant portion of CAGE expressed sequence tags mapped to 3'UTRs. This means that these tags may be expressed independently. To check if the above mentioned 3'UTRs are also expressed independently of their mRNAs, the 3'UTR sequences of these 7 genes were searched for homology to possible promoter regions, like TATA sequences. Then the sequences downstream of the putative promoters were used as queries to search the Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO) database in NCBI website, using BLAST software, in order to find cDNAs (ESTs) expressed from those 3'UTRs. It is clear that the majority of cDNAs or ESTs in GEO are not mRNAs' degradation products, because full-length mRNAs are routinely used to construct cDNA libraries [42]. Results are listed in Tab.1 (For details, see Supplementary materials). Interestingly, among all resulted cDNAs with high homology, 6 of 7 3'UTRs (except ribonucleotide reductase R2) were found to have cDNAs mapped downstream of those putative promoters, or to have cDNAs containing segments highly homologous to the query sequences (ribonucleotide reductase R1). For the α -tropomyosin and the rat mel-18, query sequences taken from their 3'UTRs also detected respective cDNAs, whose lengths were very similar with those 3'UTRs. Because the cloning procedure in preparing cDNA libraries in GEO guaranteed that the normal coding DNA strands are transcribed from all of the cDNAs [43], it is interesting that many of the ESTs have their orientations opposite with the I3'UTRs. This indicates that the formation of the I3'UTRs *in vivo* may not all be by straightforward transcription, certain recombinations may occur.

Name of the 3'UTR	Putative TATA box in 3'UTR	Number of homologous cDNAs in GEO	Animals	Cells and tissues where cDNAs are in
C/EBP β 3'UTR (NM_001285879.1; from nt:1489)	TATATATA	16	human	testis; senescent fibroblasts; total fetus; fetal heart; pregnant uterus; fetal liver; breast; ovary tumor; islet
α -tropomyosin 3'UTR (AJ000147.1)	Not found	1	human	Unknown (GenBank:F13809.1).
Mel-18 3'UTR [30]	Not found	1	rat	Unknown (GenBank [BF404720.1]).
Prohibitin 3'UTR (NM_001281496.1)	TATA	6	human	pancreas
Ribonucleotide reductase subunit R1 3'UTR (X72306.1, nucleotide 2619-3064)	TATAAAA	2	mouse	round spermatid; adult retina
C/EBP β transcript Variant 1 (HP8) 3'UTR [35]	TATA	9	human	pregnant uterus; fetal liver; fetal spleen; breast

Table 1 Expression of cDNAs from regions downstream of the putative promoters in 3'UTRs Neither promoter-like sequence nor cDNA expressed from its 3'UTR were found for the ribonucleotide reductase subunit R2. In α -tropomyosin and mel-18 3'UTRs, no TATA

box-like sequence was detected, but cDNAs homologous with their 3'UTRs were found. (For details, see *Supplementary materials)

These results showed that at least the majority in the above mentioned 3'UTRs was able to express I3'UTRs *in vivo*. For the ribonucleotide reductase subunit R2, there is no evidence that it is unable to express I3'UTR. Therefore, it is believed that I3'UTRs actually exist in human, rat and mouse cells.

On the other hand, it has been found by Mercer *et al.*[21] that the I3'UTRs exist also in fruit fly, an invertebrate. Thus it is probable that the I3'UTRs exist in most eukaryotes.

Properties of I3'UTRs known so far

As mentioned above, the properties and functions of I3'UTRs remain largely unclear. Here, based on the published literature, known functions of the I3'UTRs are discussed, assuming that the natural I3'UTRs are approximately the same as the artificial I3'UTRs in the above mentioned reports.

Subcellular localization: The mRNAs are transcribed and spliced in the nucleus, and are then transported into the cytoplasm and translated there, while bound to ribosomes in the endoplasmic reticulum. However, when the 3'UTRs are detached from their original mRNA, where are they localized?

In the study by Wang *et al.* [28], the localization of C/EBP β 3'UTR RNA was observed using a molecular beacon and fluorescent antibody under a laser confocal microscope. It was found that the C/EBP β 3'UTR RNA was bound to keratin18 (CK18) [28]. Although this 3'UTR is identical in sequence to the 3'UTR in the C/EBP β mRNA, no report on the binding of full-length C/EBP β mRNA to CK18 or to PKC ϵ was found by the author of this mini-review. If this is true, then the subcellular localization of the I3'UTR is rather different from the 3'UTR as a part of mRNA.

Figure 1 Laser confocal micrograph of revertant hepatoma cell strain Cl1, which was formed by the transfection with expression plasmid harboring the independent C/EBP β 3'UTR cDNA. The interactions between the independent C/EBP β 3'UTR RNA and keratin 18 are shown. The keratin 18 was stained with a fluorescent anti-keratin 18 antibody (green), and the independent C/EBP β 3'UTR RNA was stained with a molecular beacon to this 3'UTR RNA (red). Arrows show yellow fluorescence points in the cytoplasm, indicating that the 3'UTR RNA is located extremely closely with keratin 18, a sign of direct interactions between these two kinds of biomolecules. Cited from Wang *et al.* [28].

Influence on the expression of the mRNAs with 3'UTR that is identical to the I3'UTRs:

In the study by Liu *et al.*[26], Northern hybridizations for the total RNA of SMMC-7721 cells stably transfected by C/EBP β 3'UTR, using 32 P-labeled C/EBP β 3'UTR cDNA as a probe, revealed that there were no significant changes in the amounts of full-length C/EBP β mRNA between the transfectants and the control cells (Fig.2B in [26]). In the study by Wang *et al.*[28], Western blot studies were conducted to check the influence of the C/EBP β 3'UTR RNA to the expression of C/EBP β protein from the C/EBP β mRNA. Results showed that both the transient and stable transfections by C/EBP β 3'UTR RNA did not change the expression of the major C/EBP β protein noticeably. Therefore, the results indicated that, once detached from the mRNA, I3'UTR ceased regulating the expression of the protein products of its original mRNA.

In the case of the α -tropomyosin, it was noted that the expression of cytoskeletal proteins like tropomyosins may be incompatible with neoplasia. Cells transformed by expression of various oncogenes ceased expressing tropomyosins, whereas revertants that were no longer transformed re-expressed them. However, it was not mentioned whether or not the expression of α -tropomyosin was up-regulated in the NMU2 cells when the I3'UTR from α -tropomyosin mRNA was allowed to be expressed in them[31].

Interactions with cellular protein factors: As the I3'UTR possesses an identical sequence with the 3'UTR in the original mRNA, they may share a number of cellular interaction proteins. In fact, both species do interact with the RNA binding protein HuR and hnRNPc [29,36-38]. However, in the case of the mRNA with 3'UTR included, the interactions with RNA binding proteins affect merely the expression of the encoded protein, but in the case of I3'UTR, different effects are demonstrated, like cell growth inhibition [29].

The revertant cells, formed by treatments that lead to loss of malignancy, often show flat morphology[30,39]. Obviously, this is because the cytoskeleton underwent reorganization. In the case of the C/EBP β 3'UTR RNA, its transfection led to significant reorganization of the CK18 in the flat revertants, one of them was the Cl1 cell strain, and the appearance of these intermediate filaments in Cl1 looks like bundles and aggregates. The amounts of these bundles and aggregates were positively related to the amount of transfected C/EBP β 3'UTR RNA[28]. Therefore, the reorganization of CK18 was caused by its interaction with C/EBP β 3'UTR RNA.

Moreover, in the Cl1 strain, it was found that the C/EBP β 3'UTR RNA formed a complex with CK18 and PKC ϵ , the latter is a major oncogene, which is over-expressed in many cancers [40].

This complex was detected by using Western blots, and the phosphorylation activity of the PKC ϵ was significantly inhibited. The inhibition of PKC ϵ is undoubtedly related to the suppression of malignancy in SMMC-7721 cells [28].

Role of 3'UTRs in development: In the study by Mercer *et al.*[21], 138 3'UTRs (uaRNAs) and their original mRNA coding regions were compared, using bioinformatic tools, in mouse embryonic stem (ES) cells and in mouse embryonic ovary and testis. About half of the 3'UTRs and their corresponding mRNA were found expressed differently. The origin of these 3'UTRs may be from differential expression of alternatively spliced mRNAs, transcriptionally independent of the coding region, or post-transcriptional processing from the mRNA. Further bioinformatic analysis indicated that 3'UTRs' expression is a regulated process rather than a by-product of host gene expression.

On the other hand, the expression of Col1a1 gene, the procollagen type I alpha 1 chain, was checked by *in situ* hybridization in whole-mouse embryo, using specific RNA probes to the coding exon and two parts in 3'UTR sequences, respectively. Results showed that the expression of the coding region persisted during ossification, whereas no expression of the 3'UTR was detected. Moreover, the most distal 3'UTR probe revealed expression of the targeted sequence in the dorsal root ganglia, where the expression was not detected by a coding probe or the other 3'UTR probe. Therefore the different expression profiles of the Col1a1 exons and its 3'UTRs verified that 3'UTRs are independently expressed in a tissue-specific manner. This means that the 3'UTR plays a distinct role, different from the full-length mRNA, in the embryonic development[21].

In the case of human C/EBP β 3'UTR RNA, 16 ESTs were found using BLAST search in GEO with the portion of 3'UTR, downstream of the typical TATA box, as the query sequence. These ESTs were expressed in human testis, senescent fibroblasts, fetal heart, fetal liver, pregnant uterus, breast, islet, pancreas, ovary tumor, and neuroblastoma [Tab.1 and Supplementary materials]. Similarly, in the C/EBP α transcript variant 1, the ESTs homologous with its 3'UTR downstream of the putative promoter were found from pregnant uterus, fetal liver, fetal spleen, and other unknown RNA sources [Tab.1 and Supplementary materials]. Although the expression in other organs and tissues cannot be excluded, these situations of ESTs suggest that 3'UTRs may have functions in cellular growth and development, senescence and secretion.

Tumor suppression activity of 3'UTRs: what does it mean? It is now well understood that under normal circumstances, the proto-oncogenes play roles necessary for normal cellular growth, proliferation, and survival, and their normal expression is under control of a group of controlling genes, like p53 *etc* (so-called "intrinsic tumor suppression activities"). When mutations in those proto-oncogenes occur, or other factors appear that cause over-expression of them, they become oncogenes and give rise to uncontrolled cellular growth and resistance to apoptosis, *i.e.* tumorigenesis [41]. The tumor suppression is thus a kind of cellular action to

control the expression and function of various genes responsible for cell growth and differentiation.

Therefore, the 3'UTRs are also such a kind of cellular growth/differentiation regulators. As the majority of oncogenes are relevant to cellular signal transduction pathways that consist of protein kinases, the molecular mechanisms of the actions of 3'UTRs may be looked for in the interactions between the latter and protein kinases as well as other transcription factors. The interaction of C/EBP β 3'UTR RNA with PKC ϵ and CK18 is an example.

What is unknown now?

When the tumor suppression activity of the 3'UTRs independent of their mRNAs was only just discovered, its significance was not generally understood. It was even ignored because the only known 3'UTR was an integral part of the mRNA, and its functions were merely the regulation of expression of the mRNA. Moreover, unfortunately, many studies on the 3'UTRs, like those mentioned above, were not continued further, so that the truth on the 3'UTR has not been shown up until now, when the article on the expression of distinct RNAs from 3'UTR[21] was published.

This mini-review has demonstrated that the majority of the DNAs from the studied 3'UTRs have homologous ESTs that map to positions downstream of putative promoters in those 3'UTRs. This fact means that 3'UTRs, at least in part, are transcribed from the 3'UTRs of genes [Supplementary materials]. And it is believable that the 3'UTRs may probably exist in most, if not all, eukaryotes.

What is the normal function(s) of the 3'UTRs and what are their molecular mechanisms? At present nothing can be said, except that a great deal of investigations need to be performed. For example, first, how are the 3'UTRs expressed, and what is their difference in expression from their original mRNAs? What are the characteristics of their expression in various organs and tissues and in various stages of the development? What regulates the expression of 3'UTRs? Second, what are the targets of regulation of 3'UTRs? It is well known that in cells there are very large amounts of regulating factors, both protein and RNA in nature, why are the 3'UTRs needed? Third, a very interesting problem is the inter-relationships between 3'UTRs and miRNAs. miRNAs regulate mRNA translation through binding to the sites on 3'UTRs; as these sites also exist in the 3'UTRs, do 3'UTRs interact with miRNAs also through these sites? What is the result of such interactions? Do these interactions cause degradation of the 3'UTRs? *etc.* All these problems merit further and deeper investigations, and results of these investigations will certainly lead to a great step forward in the understanding on RNA biology.

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Supplementary Materials

The supplementary materials for this article is available at http://biohelikon.org/manuscript/2348-3741-2-a15_supp_material.pdf

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